

Grignard Reaction of Isothiocyanates : Synthesis of Thioamides. Part I

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In order to synthesize thioamides, Grignard reaction of isothiocyanates was investigated and found to be an ideal method for their synthesis.

In order to prepare various thioamides required for study, Grignard reaction of isothiocyanates has been studied and has been found to be a good general method. Grignard reagent reacts with the isothiocyanates forming a convenient route to the formation of thioamides. The reaction of phenyl isothiocyanate with methyl magnesium iodide was first studied by Warrall¹ who suggested the course of reaction as shown in chart I.

This assumption of mechanism of reaction has been confirmed by Gilman² who by alkylation of the intermediate addition product III showed that the Grignard reagent added to the thiocarbonyl group of the isothiocyanate.

In the present investigation a large excess of the Grignard reagent in ether was used for the optimum yield of the thioamides. This excess seems to have no apparent effect on the addition complex, but it is possible, we believe, in this way to direct the reaction more completely in the desired direction. It also helps to avoid losses due to the action of small amounts of moisture, carbon dioxide etc. The addition complex III was also isolated for a number of compounds where it was a solid. It did not give a definite melting point but decomposed at high temperature. To follow the course of reaction dimethyl sulphate was added to this complex to get the alkylated products. This particular aspect of this reaction is under investigation and will be communicated shortly.

1. D. E., Warrall, *J. Amer Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **47**, 2974.
2. H. Gilman and C. R. Kinney, *J. Amer Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 493.

The reaction was found to occur very readily with evolution of heat and was apparently completed in a few minutes. Long standing of the reactants was found to improve the yields. Thus methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl, *n*-butyl, *n*-amyl, isoamyl and *n*-hexyl magnesium iodides were condensed with *p*-bromophenyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolyl, *o*- and *p*-anisyl isothiocyanates to get thioamides of the general formula VI.

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting points are uncorrected.

Various Grignard reagents were prepared by the standard methods known. Following example shows the general method of preparing thioamides.

Synthesis of N-p-Tolyl-thiobutyramide: To a warm solution of *n*-Propyl magnesium iodide (0.4 mole) in anhydrous ether taken in a round bottom flask fitted with a double surface condenser and a guard tube, was added *p*-Tolyl isothiocyanate (0.17 mole) dropwise. Sufficient heat was evolved to cause vigorous boiling of the ether solution which was moderated by cooling in a water bath. In about 30 mins after the addition, bulky precipitates were obtained. The reaction mixture was left overnight and the product obtained was filtered by suction, washed with ether and the dry product was added to hydrochloric acid (1 : 1) containing crushed ice with constant stirring. A solid separated which was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol. It melted at 80°. The yield of the product was 90% calculated on the basis of isothiocyanate.

All thioamides thus prepared were obtained in the range of 75 to 90% yield.

TABLE
N-Aryl alkyl thioamides (VI)

X	R	M.P.°C	Name of product	Mol. Formula	Analysis (Calc/found)	
					N per cent	S
1. <i>p</i> -Cl	CH ₃	142	<i>N-p</i> -chlorophenyl thioacetamide	C ₆ H ₉ ClNS	7.5/7.4	17.2/17.1
2. <i>p</i> -Br	..	154	<i>N-p</i> -bromophenyl thioacetamide	C ₆ H ₉ BrNS	6.0/6.1	15.6/15.5
3. <i>p</i> -CH ₃	..	68	<i>N-p</i> -tolyl thioacetamide	C ₉ H ₁₁ NS	8.5/8.4	19.4/19.1
4. <i>o</i> -CH ₃	..	148	<i>N-o</i> -tolyl thioacetamide	do	8.5/8.4	19.4/19.3
5. <i>m</i> -CH ₃	..	42	<i>N-m</i> -tolyl thioacetamide	do	8.5/8.2	19.4/19.3
6. <i>o</i> -CH ₃ O	..	98	<i>N-o</i> -anisyl thioacetamide	C ₉ H ₁₁ NOS	7.7/7.6	17.7/17.5
7. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	..	143	<i>N-p</i> -anisyl thioacetamide	do	7.7/7.4	17.7/17.4
8. <i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂ H ₅	80	<i>N-p</i> -chlorophenyl thio-propionamide	C ₉ H ₁₀ ClNS	7.4/7.5	16.9/16.7
9. <i>p</i> -Br	..	61	<i>N-p</i> -bromophenyl thio-propionamide	C ₉ H ₁₀ BrNS	5.7/5.6	13.1/13.0
10. <i>o</i> -CH ₃	..	185 d	<i>N-o</i> -tolyl thiopropionamide	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ NS	7.6/7.5	18.8/18.7
11. <i>m</i> -CH ₃	..	140	<i>N-m</i> -tolyl thiopropionamide	do	7.6/7.6	18.8/18.6
12. <i>p</i> -CH ₃	..	180 d	<i>N-p</i> -tolyl thiopropionamide	do	7.6/7.5	18.8/18.4
13. <i>o</i> -CH ₃ O	..	160	<i>N-o</i> -anisyl thiopropionamide	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ NOS	7.2/7.1	16.4/16.1

TABLE (Contd.)

N-Aryl alkyl thioamides (VI)

X	R	M.P°C	Name of product	Mol. Formula	Analysis (Calc/Found) per cent	
					N	S
14. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	C ₂ H ₅	150	<i>N-p</i> -anisyl thiopropionamide	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ NOS	7.2/7.0	16.4/16.3
15. <i>p</i> -Cl	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	114	<i>N-p</i> -chlorophenyl thio- butyramide	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ ClNS	6.5/6.6	14.9/14.8
16. <i>p</i> -Br	„	210 d	<i>N-p</i> -bromophenyl thio- butyramide	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ BrNS	5.4/5.3	12.4/12.1
17. <i>o</i> -CH ₃	„	175	<i>N-o</i> -tolyl thiobutyramide	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NS	7.2/7.1	16.5/16.4
18. <i>m</i> -CH ₃	„	146	<i>N-m</i> -tolyl thiobutyramide	do	7.2/7.2	16.5/16.3
19. <i>p</i> -CH ₃	„	80	<i>N-p</i> -tolyl thiobutyramide	do	7.2/7.1	16.5/16.3
20. <i>o</i> -CH ₃ O	„	65	<i>N-o</i> -anisyl thiobutyramide	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NOS	6.7/6.5	15.2/15.0
21. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	„	60	<i>N-p</i> -anisyl thiobutyramide	do	6.7/6.5	15.2/15.2
22. <i>p</i> -Cl	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	107	<i>N-p</i> -chlorophenyl thio- valeramide	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ ClNS	6.1/6.0	14.1/14.0
23. <i>p</i> -Br	„	112	<i>N-p</i> -bromophenyl thio- valeramide	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ BrNS	5.2/5.1	11.9/11.7
24. <i>o</i> -CH ₃	„	184 d	<i>N-o</i> -tolyl thiovaleramide	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NS	6.8/6.7	15.4/15.3
25. <i>m</i> -CH ₃	„	119	<i>N-m</i> -tolyl thiovaleramide	do	6.8/6.6	15.4/15.2
26. <i>p</i> -CH ₃	„	200 d	<i>N-p</i> -tolyl thiovaleramide	do	6.8/6.6	15.4/15.4
27. <i>o</i> -CH ₃ O	„	145	<i>N-o</i> -anisyl thiovaleramide	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NOS	6.6/6.4	15.0/15.0
28. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	„	63	<i>N-p</i> -anisyl thiovaleramide	do	6.6/6.5	15.0/14.9
29. <i>p</i> -Cl	<i>n</i> -C ₅ H ₁₁	179	<i>N-p</i> -chlorophenyl thio- caproic amide	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ ClNS	5.9/5.7	13.5/13.4
30. <i>p</i> -Br	„	92	<i>N-p</i> -bromophenyl thio- caproic amide	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ BrNS	4.9/4.9	11.2/11.1
31. <i>o</i> -CH ₃	„	170 d	<i>N-o</i> -tolyl thiocaproic amide	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ NS	6.3/6.2	14.4/14.2
32. <i>m</i> -CH ₃	„	165	<i>N-m</i> -tolyl thiocaproic amide	do	6.3/6.3	14.4/14.2
33. <i>p</i> -CH ₃	„	158 d	<i>N-p</i> -tolyl thiocaproic amide	do	6.3/6.3	14.4/14.1
34. <i>o</i> -CH ₃ O	„	128	<i>N-o</i> -anisyl thiocaproic amide	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ NOS	5.9/5.7	13.5/13.5
35. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	„	140	<i>N-p</i> -anisyl thiocaproic amide	do	5.9/5.7	13.5/13.2
36. <i>p</i> -Cl	<i>iso</i> -C ₅ H ₁₁	135 d	<i>N-p</i> -chlorophenyl thio- isocaproic amide	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ ClNS	5.8/5.7	13.5/13.3
37. <i>p</i> -Br	„	120	<i>N-p</i> -bromophenyl thio- isocaproic amide	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ BrNS	4.9/4.8	12.2/11.0
38. <i>o</i> -CH ₃	„	140 d	<i>N-o</i> -tolyl thio-isocaproic amide	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ NS	6.3/6.2	14.4/14.2
39. <i>m</i> -CH ₃	„	111	<i>N-m</i> -tolyl thio-isocaproic amide	do	6.3/6.1	14.4/14.3
40. <i>p</i> -CH ₃	„	180 d	<i>N-p</i> -tolyl thio-isocaproic amide	do	6.3/6.2	14.4/14.2
41. <i>o</i> -CH ₃ O	„	136	<i>N-o</i> -anisyl thio-isocaproic amide	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ NOS	5.9/5.7	13.5/13.4
42. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	„	70	<i>N-p</i> -anisyl thio-isocaproic amide	do	5.9/5.8	13.5/13.5
43. <i>p</i> -Cl	<i>n</i> -C ₆ H ₁₃	110	<i>N-p</i> -chlorophenyl thio- heptanoic amide	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ ClNS	5.5/5.4	12.5/12.4
44. <i>p</i> -Br	„	115	<i>N-p</i> -bromophenyl thio- heptanoic amide	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ BrNS	4.7/4.6	10.7/10.7
45. <i>o</i> -CH ₃	„	162 d	<i>N-o</i> -tolyl thioheptanoic amide	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ NS	5.9/5.7	13.6/13.5
46. <i>m</i> -CH ₃	„	paste	<i>N-m</i> -tolyl thioheptanoic amide	do	-not analysed-	
47. <i>p</i> -CH ₃	„	107	<i>N-p</i> -tolyl thioheptanoic amide	do	5.9/5.6	13.6/13.6
48. <i>o</i> -CH ₃ O	„	134	<i>N-o</i> -anisyl thioheptanoic amide	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ NOS	5.6/5.6	12.7/12.8
49. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	„	68	<i>N-p</i> -anisyl thioheptanoic amide	do	5.6/5.8	12.7/12.3

